

**FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF READING NEEDS BASED ON
SECONDARY SOURCES OF INFORMATION**

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Abstract: The article reveals the features of the bibliographic activity of the Alisher Navoi National Library of Uzbekistan in the preparation of secondary sources of information that contribute to meeting the diverse information needs of readers.

Keywords: information needs, bibliographic indexes, libraries, user interests.

As a social institution, the library should create opportunities for members of society to meet their information needs, which can be very diverse and relate to different areas of human activity. By providing its users with information, the library thereby contributes to the growth of the material well-being of society, but its main purpose is that its resources are the basis for the formation and development of various readers' interests and needs.

Therefore, the goal put forward by the International Library Organization IFLA - "a sustainable future for all through knowledge and information" [1] can be called timely.

A modern library as an information, cultural, educational institution that has an organized fund of documents and provides them for temporary use, as well as implementing other library services, has a set of information resources that allow information services. Each library forms a set of information resources in accordance with the goals and objectives set for it by society, as well as the main needs of the served contingent of users.

The Alisher Navoi National Library of Uzbekistan today is a nationwide universal information and library institution organizing and carrying out information and library activities in the Republic of Uzbekistan in the interests of the development of national and world culture, art, science and education. The information resources of the library should also include resources of its own generation, which are a complex and multifaceted group of resources. Moreover, the resources of its own generation are not only scanned texts of the most popular individual printed documents and not only digitized collections, but also bibliographic resources, for example, catalogs - both

traditional and electronic, other bibliographic manuals, for example, indexes, both published in typographic way and unpublished.

The National Library on the selected profile carefully collects published and unpublished documents (primary documents), and its bibliographic information resources (secondary sources of information) most often reflect the available document fund. Bibliographic information is recorded on solid media and posted on electronic networks.

Improving the quality and efficiency of bibliographic manuals using digital technologies, library specialists prepare full-text electronic bio-bibliographic indexes not only on traditional media, but also on CDs. The signs are dedicated to prominent public figures, scientists, writers, representatives of science, art and culture of Uzbekistan. The peculiarity of compiling a pointer on a CD in parallel is that it gives access to primary sources of information from hundreds of magazines, newspaper articles, scientific works of figures in a digitized format, thereby facilitating research search for the user.

Bibliographic indexes are compiled for a wide range of users in Uzbek and Russian, containing information not only from print media, but also from media publications (phonograph records, audio, and video). One of these sources is the bibliographic index "Catalog of literature receipts to the Alisher Navoi National Library of Uzbekistan" [2], issued once every six months and reflecting publications in all areas of knowledge based on receipts to the National Library of Uzbekistan. The main task of the publication is to inform the general public and library users about the new literature. The index also assists library and information service workers in reference and information services for specialists. Bibliographic records of documents are located based on the "Universal decimal classification," are equipped with ciphers of the National Library of Uzbekistan.

An employee of the reference and information service, the fund and catalog processing service, and the national database bibliography formation service take part in the compilation of the bibliographic index.

The bibliographic index "Fiction translated into Uzbek" (Tashkent, 2019) [3] aims to inform readers about fiction publications, including children's fiction published in Uzbek in Uzbekistan. The index consists of several sections: 1. Collections of works by writers from different countries and peoples. 2. Folklore. 3. Collections of works by writers of foreign and fraternal countries (individual works of authors). The material is arranged in alphabetical order, literary and artistic collections with disclosure of

content are highlighted in the first place inside each section, and then bibliographic records for the works of individual authors are presented. For the convenience of use by employees of information and library institutions, writers, translators, literary scholars, students and all interested issues of literature, the manual is equipped with a "Name index of authors," "Name index of translators," "Title index."

In recent years, the library has issued more than twenty full-text bio-bibliographic indexes of a new type dedicated to outstanding public figures, scientists and writers, figures of science, art and culture of Uzbekistan. The modernized direction of such manuals was the creation of a full-text electronic index, which presents all its advantages over the printed format. The peculiarity of such an index is that all the scientist's labor activity is presented in a digitized format.

Full-text bio-bibliographic indexes are dedicated to famous composers, poets, collectors of works of folk and modern Uzbek music. These, Mutal Burkhanov, Mukhtar Ashrafi and Yunus Rajabi are musical artists who have devoted their whole lives to serving the arts. The first disc was released in 2016 and is dedicated to the anniversary date of Mutal Burkhanov ("100th anniversary of birth"). The index consists of musical editions of his works, phonograph records and articles from periodicals about the composer. For example, in order to listen to the song "Guzal Fergana" performed by Tamara Khanum, hold down the Ctrl key + click with the mouse (left mouse button).

The second disc in 2017 is dedicated to the anniversary date of Yunus Rajabi (120th anniversary), a singer and composer in the field of musical folklore of Uzbekistan. The pointer scheme is the same as on the first disc, but in addition to the audio material, there is a documentary dedicated to the 120th anniversary of the great composer. The material was collected not only from the funds of the National Library, but also from the funds of the library of the State Conservatory of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The third disc in 2017 is dedicated to Mukhtar Ashrafi (105th anniversary), composer, conductor and teacher, founder of modern Uzbek music and national opera art. On the disc, the scheme is the same, the works in the musical edition and his famous songs and romances are digitized.

This type of information support, such as a full-text bibliographic index, facilitates access to information and makes it possible for those wishing to find the necessary works without difficulty, and saving time.

Bibliographic indexes dedicated to the ancient cities of Uzbekistan, presented on the website of the National Bank of Uzbekistan named after A. Navoi, for example, this index "Khiva is an incomparable pearl of oriental architecture" (Tashkent, 2022) (<https://einfo.lib.uz/library/pdf>) [4]. The index was created on the basis of archival documents of the Central State Archive of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Institute of Oriental Studies named after Beruni, the Fund of the State Museum of the History of Peoples of Uzbekistan, the Fund of the Museum-Reserve of the Khiva Fortress Ichan, the Russian State Military Historical Archive (Asian part of the General Staff), the Central State Historical Archive of St. Petersburg, the Institute of Oriental Studies RAS. It contains not only handwritten books [5], but also Internet resources [6] dedicated to Khiva, in total more than 1.5 thousand documents telling based on historical documents about this wonderful city and attracting the attention of a wide range of users.

Among the bibliographic indexes of the Alisher Navoi National Library of Uzbekistan there are also indexes intended for specialists. Sources of information included in the index "System of transport industries and means of Uzbekistan" [7] are contained in the fund of the National Library and Information and Library Centers, as well as materials from the Annals of the Press of Uzbekistan. The index contains data from 6295 literary units and reflects the entire history of the transport industry countries from 1887 to 2020. The index contains information from brochures, books, abstracts, dissertations, as well as newspaper and magazine materials in uzbek, russian, karakalpak, tajik and other foreign languages. For ease of use, documents in sections are arranged first by language and then alphabetically. The reference apparatus of this manual includes the "Author Index."

All accumulated information about the reality surrounding us, which is recorded on material media or in any other form that provides transmission in time and space between different consumers is an information resource disclosed through bibliographic information. Bibliographic information is used at the initial stages of research, educational and practical purposes, as well as to obtain information about new documents. Modern bibliographic resources are presented both in traditional (printed) form and in electronic form.

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